

Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

Op. 6 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7863726>

Diego Casadei
(April 2005)

The musical score is arranged in two systems. The first system includes parts for B♭ Trumpet 1, B♭ Trumpet 2, Alto Sax., Bari. Sax., and Tuba. The second system includes parts for B♭ Tpt. 1, B♭ Tpt. 2, A. Sax., B. Sax., and Tba. The score is in 3/4 time with a tempo marking of quarter note = 90. The key signature has one flat (B♭). The first system shows the initial measures, with the saxophones and tuba starting a rhythmic pattern. The second system shows the continuation of the piece, with the trumpets and saxophones playing more complex melodic lines.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

15

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

19

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

Musical score for measures 23-26. The score is for five instruments: B $\flat$ Tpt. 1, B $\flat$ Tpt. 2, A. Sx., B. Sx., and Tba. The key signature is B $\flat$ major. Measure 23 starts with a treble clef and a key signature change to B $\flat$ major. The B $\flat$ Tpt. 1 part has rests in measures 23-25 and enters in measure 26. The B $\flat$ Tpt. 2 part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 23-25 and rests in measure 26. The A. Sx. part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 23-25 and rests in measure 26. The B. Sx. part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 23-25 and rests in measure 26. The Tba. part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 23-25 and rests in measure 26. The score ends with a double bar line and repeat dots.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

Musical score for measures 27-30. The score is for five instruments: B $\flat$ Tpt. 1, B $\flat$ Tpt. 2, A. Sx., B. Sx., and Tba. The key signature is B $\flat$ major. Measure 27 starts with a treble clef and a key signature change to B $\flat$ major. The B $\flat$ Tpt. 1 part has rests in measures 27-28 and enters in measure 29. The B $\flat$ Tpt. 2 part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 27-28 and rests in measure 29. The A. Sx. part has a rest in measure 27, followed by a 4-measure improvisation in measures 28-31. The B. Sx. part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 27-28 and rests in measure 29. The Tba. part plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in measures 27-28 and rests in measure 29. The score ends with a double bar line and repeat dots.

(improvvisa 4 battute)

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

(improvvisa 4 battute)

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

31

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

35

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

39

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

43

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B $\flat$ Tpt. 1

B $\flat$ Tpt. 2

A. Sx.

B. Sx.

Tba.

B♭ Tpt. 1

B♭ Tpt. 2

A. Sax.

B. Sax.

Tba.

63

Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

B $\flat$ Trumpet 1

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1 $\text{♩} = 90$ 3

9

14

20

28 4
(improvvisa 4 battute)

36

41

46

50

54

58

62 2

Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

B♭ Trumpet 2

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1 $\bullet = 90$ 4

9

15

22

28

37

44

49

54

58

62

Alto Sax. Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

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1 = 90

2

7

11

16

21

26 4
(improvvisa 4 battute)

33

38

44

49

54

58

62

Bari. Sax. Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

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1 = 90

5

9

13

19

25

30

34

40

45

49

53

59

63

Quintetto sudamericano (v. 2)

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Tuba

1 $\text{♩} = 90$

4

7

13

19

25

31

37

43

49

55

61

